

Radar Interference Mitigation: A Review

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Abstract—Radar systems are increasingly critical in various applications, from automotive safety to air traffic control and military operations. However, radar interference remains a significant challenge, impacting the reliability and accuracy of radar systems. This review paper provides a comprehensive examination of radar interference mitigation techniques, emphasizing their practical applications, advantages, and limitations. Specific examples such as automotive radar experiencing mutual interference in dense traffic or weather radars facing clutter from wind turbines are discussed. We explore classical approaches such as filtering and time-domain gating, alongside advanced methods leveraging machine learning and adaptive signal processing. The discussion synthesizes current research trends and identifies gaps, offering insights for future development in the field.

Index Terms—radar, interference, signal processing, target detection, deep learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Radar technology is integral to modern systems, offering robust solutions for detection, ranging, and imaging. For instance, automotive radars are used for collision avoidance, while air traffic control systems rely on radar to manage the safe movement of aircraft. With the proliferation of radars in dense environments, such as urban areas and vehicular networks, interference between radar systems has emerged as a critical issue. Mutual interference between automotive radars in multi-lane traffic or cross-interference from nearby systems can degrade performance, causing data inaccuracies and, in extreme cases, rendering radars inoperable. Addressing this challenge necessitates effective interference mitigation strategies.

Radar systems operate by transmitting electromagnetic waves and analyzing the reflected signals to detect objects and measure their distance, speed, and other characteristics. However, the increasing density of radar systems in various applications has led to a rise in interference incidents. For example, automotive radars in close proximity can interfere with each other, leading to false detections or missed targets. Similarly, weather radars can experience clutter from wind turbines, affecting the accuracy of weather predictions. These challenges highlight the need for robust interference mitigation techniques to ensure the reliable operation of radar systems.

The significance of radar technology extends beyond automotive and weather applications. In military operations, radar systems are crucial for surveillance, target tracking, and missile guidance. In maritime navigation, radars help in detecting other vessels and obstacles, ensuring safe passage. The versatility and importance of radar technology underscore

the critical need to address interference issues that can compromise their performance [46], [47], [50].

Recent studies have explored various aspects of radar interference and mitigation techniques. For instance, the work by Alland et al. [1] discusses the challenges of radar-to-radar interference in automotive applications and proposes solutions to enhance radar performance in dense traffic environments. Similarly, the study by Xu and Wei [2] presents a time-domain signal reconstruction method for FMCW radar systems to mitigate interference. These studies highlight the ongoing efforts to develop effective interference mitigation strategies.

To ensure a comprehensive review, a systematic methodology was adopted:

- 1) Peer-reviewed journals, conference proceedings, and technical reports from 1997 to 2024 were analyzed. For example, recent papers on FMCW radar interference and machine learning applications were included. The literature review focused on identifying key trends, challenges, and advancements in radar interference mitigation. Sources were selected based on their relevance, impact, and contribution to the field. This extensive review process ensured that the most significant and up-to-date research was considered, providing a solid foundation for the analysis presented in this paper. The review included studies on various interference mitigation techniques, such as adaptive signal processing, machine learning, and frequency agility. For instance, the work by Melvin [3] provides an overview of adaptive interference mitigation techniques and their applications in radar systems. Additionally, the study by Huang et al. [4] explores the use of range-Doppler sparse regularization for interference mitigation in automotive FMCW radar. These references were instrumental in understanding the current state of the art and identifying areas for further research.
- 2) Mitigation techniques were classified into classical and advanced methods, such as hardware-based solutions and software-driven machine learning models. Classical methods include filtering techniques and time-domain gating, while advanced methods encompass adaptive signal processing and machine learning techniques. This categorization helps in understanding the evolution of interference mitigation strategies and their respective strengths and limitations. By organizing the techniques into these categories, the review provides a clear framework for comparing and contrasting different approaches. The categorization also considered the application domains of the mitigation techniques. For example, filtering techniques are commonly used in automotive radar systems to suppress mutual interference, while

adaptive signal processing methods are employed in military radar systems to counteract jamming signals. This contextual understanding of the techniques' applications further enhances the comprehensiveness of the review.

- 3) Performance metrics such as interference suppression efficiency, computational complexity, and implementation feasibility were considered. Case studies from automotive and weather radar systems were included. These metrics provide a basis for evaluating the effectiveness of different mitigation techniques and their suitability for various applications. For instance, interference suppression efficiency measures the ability of a technique to reduce or eliminate interference, while computational complexity assesses the resources required for implementation. By considering these metrics, the review offers a comprehensive evaluation of each technique's practical applicability.

The comparison metrics were derived from both theoretical analyses and experimental results reported in the literature. For example, the study by Alland et al. [1] provides a detailed analysis of the signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) and its impact on radar performance. Similarly, the work by MathWorks [6] demonstrates the use of frequency agility techniques to mitigate interference in radar systems. These studies provided valuable insights into the performance and feasibility of various interference mitigation techniques.

This review paper aims to:

- 1) Summarize the sources and effects of radar interference.
- 2) Analyze classical and emerging interference mitigation techniques.
- 3) Highlight future research directions to advance radar robustness.

II. METHODOLOGY

The MOSARIM project [39] conducted a comprehensive study of interference in radar systems that focused on interference mitigation. Within the project modeling, simulations, and tests of interference to automotive radar of various mitigation techniques are performed. Interference mitigation techniques were categorized into six major domains: polarization, time, frequency, coding, space (e.g., beamforming), and strategic approaches. Strategic approaches involved detecting interference and adjusting waveform parameters [24] and/or beamscanning in response, as well as detecting and excising interference followed by repairing the received signal in the time, frequency, or joint-time-frequency domains. Another strategic technique considered was intervehicle communication, which negotiates noninterfering radar parameters (e.g., time or frequency slots). Except for the polarization domain, many techniques described in the MOSARIM project required substantial signal processing to handle complex waveforms, adaptively null interference, and/or detect and excise interference. Techniques with the highest signal processing complexity included digital beamforming with adaptive nulling, time-frequency transforming with interference detection and excision, and

space-time adaptive processing. MOSARIM concluded that [39]: "To assure an $\frac{I}{N}$ level of 0 or -10 dB, reliable mitigation techniques in the order of (a minimum of) 50 dB mitigation margin are needed." and individual mitigation techniques are insufficient on their own; multiple techniques must be applied. As the volume of automotive radars increases, it may be advantageous to regulate the assignment of polarization and frequency bands based on the radar application/type (e.g., SRR, MRR, or LRR) and the mounting location on the vehicle. For instance, different subbands could be used in various directions (front, back, and side) along with different polarizations [5].

A. Classical Approaches

1) *Hardware Approaches*: Hardware approaches involve designing specialized transceivers [33], [34] and other hardware components to mitigate interference. These approaches focus on optimizing the hardware design to enhance radar performance and reduce susceptibility to interference.

2) *Filtering Techniques*: Filtering is a foundational technique, leveraging frequency or spatial filters to suppress interference [35]. For example, bandpass filters target specific frequency ranges to isolate desired signals in FMCW radars, while spatial filtering uses beamforming [22], [28] to nullify interference from known directions. A notable application is phased array radar systems using spatial filters to track aircraft while ignoring ground clutter.

Filtering techniques are widely used due to their simplicity and effectiveness. Bandpass filters, for instance, are designed to pass signals within a specific frequency range while attenuating signals outside this range. This approach is particularly useful in FMCW radars, where interference from other sources can be reduced by targeting specific frequency ranges. Spatial filtering, on the other hand, uses beamforming techniques to nullify interference from known directions. Phased array radar systems, for example, use spatial filters to track aircraft while ignoring ground clutter. These techniques are effective in scenarios where the interference sources are well-defined and can be isolated using frequency or spatial characteristics.

Carrick et al. [42] explored methods for suppressing interference by leveraging spectral redundancies in orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) signals. They utilized time-varying frequency shift filters, known as TV-FRESH filters, to mitigate linear frequency modulated radar interference.

3) *Time-Domain Gating*: This approach mitigates interference by identifying and removing corrupted time segments. For example, pulsed radars can discard segments of the signal overlapping with interference. While simple and effective, time-domain gating is less effective in scenarios with continuous interference, such as urban vehicular environments.

Time-domain gating is a straightforward technique that involves identifying and removing corrupted time segments from the radar signal. Pulsed radars, for example, can discard

segments of the signal that overlap with interference. This approach is effective in scenarios where the interference is intermittent and can be isolated in the time domain. However, time-domain gating is less suitable for scenarios with continuous interference, such as urban vehicular environments, where the interference is persistent and cannot be easily isolated. In such cases, more advanced techniques are required to achieve effective interference mitigation.

In [45], a zeroing method has been proposed, which involves identifying and removing interference by setting a threshold above the background noise level. Any time-domain samples that exceed this threshold are effectively nullified by being set to zero. Uysal [44] proposed a time-domain approach to decompose signals, aiming to separate the automotive radar interference signal from the signal of interest. Bechter et al. [26] first estimated signal parameters from interferer, then reconstructed and subtracted the estimated interference signal. Generally, these approaches face significant challenges, as they require highly precise detection of the interference location, its duration, and other characteristics. In summary, traditional interference suppression techniques have three main limitations: (1) reliance on domain knowledge and specific interference characteristics; (2) inability to generalize; and (3) complexity due to the need for precise interference location detection. Several thresholding-based algorithms have also been proposed to detect the disrupted signal samples in time-domain [20], [36], [51].

4) *Interpolation Algorithms*: Interpolation algorithms are used to reconstruct missing or corrupted segments of the time-domain signal. These algorithms estimate the missing data points based on the surrounding data, providing a continuous and smooth signal. Common interpolation methods include linear interpolation, spline interpolation, and polynomial interpolation. For example, spline interpolation uses piecewise polynomials to estimate the missing data points, providing a smooth and continuous signal reconstruction. These algorithms are particularly useful in scenarios where the interference is intermittent and can be isolated in the time domain. In [30], the disrupted signal segments are interpolated through auto-regressive model based method, where the detected disrupted samples are interpolated by the iterative method with an adaptive thresholding algorithm (IMAT) in [49].

B. Advanced Approaches

1) *Adaptive Signal Processing*: Adaptive techniques, such as Wiener filtering and least mean squares (LMS) algorithms, dynamically adjust to changing interference patterns, enhancing robustness. For example, Wiener filtering can optimize the signal-to-noise ratio in dynamic scenarios like naval radar systems facing multipath interference.

Adaptive signal processing techniques are designed to dynamically adjust to changing interference patterns, enhancing the robustness of radar systems. Wiener filtering, for example, is an adaptive technique that optimizes the signal-to-noise ratio in dynamic scenarios. This approach is particularly useful in naval radar systems, where multipath

interference from the sea surface can degrade radar performance. By dynamically adjusting the filter parameters, Wiener filtering can effectively mitigate interference and improve radar performance. Similarly, LMS algorithms are adaptive techniques that adjust the filter coefficients based on the error signal, providing robust interference mitigation in dynamic environments.

An adaptive noise canceller [56] is implemented to reduce interference within the positive frequency spectrum of the range profile. This is achieved by using the correlated interference present in the negative frequency spectrum as a reference.

2) *Compressed Sensing*: Compressed sensing is a signal processing technique that reconstructs a signal from a small number of samples, exploiting the sparsity of the signal in some domain [11], [12]. This approach is particularly useful for radar systems, where the signal is often sparse in the time or frequency domain. Compressed sensing algorithms, such as convex optimization, greedy algorithms, and Bayesian methods, can reconstruct the signal with high accuracy from a limited number of samples. For example, convex optimization algorithms, such as Basis Pursuit, solve an optimization problem to find the sparsest solution that fits the observed data. Greedy algorithms, such as Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP), iteratively select the most significant components of the signal to reconstruct it. Bayesian methods, such as Bayesian Compressive Sensing (BCS) [13], use probabilistic models to estimate the signal and its sparsity pattern. These algorithms have been successfully applied to radar signal reconstruction, providing accurate and efficient interference mitigation.

3) *Interference Mitigation with Communication Techniques*: Interference mitigation can also be achieved through communication techniques, such as RadarMAC [16], RadCom [14], and RadChat [15]. These techniques leverage the communication capabilities of radar systems to coordinate and mitigate interference [40], [41]. RadCom, or Radar Communication, integrates radar and communication functionalities to reduce mutual interference. This approach uses frequency division multiplexing to separate radar and communication signals, allowing them to coexist without interference. RadCom systems can dynamically adjust the timing and frequency of radar transmissions based on communication signals, reducing the likelihood of interference. RadChat is a distributed networking protocol designed to mitigate interference among FMCW-based automotive radars. It uses radar and communication cooperation to coordinate radar transmissions and reduce mutual interference. RadChat can significantly reduce radar mutual interference in single-hop vehicular networks, improving the performance and reliability of automotive radar systems.

4) *Machine Learning Techniques*: Machine learning (ML) techniques are increasingly being employed for radar interference mitigation due to their ability to learn from data and adapt to new interference patterns [23], [27]. Supervised learning models, such as support vector machines (SVMs), are used to classify interference types for mitigation. These

models are trained on labeled datasets, where different types of interference are annotated, allowing the model to learn the characteristics of each interference type. Unsupervised methods, such as clustering, are used to detect anomalies in radar signals. These methods do not require labeled data and can identify patterns and clusters in the data that correspond to different interference types. For instance, supervised learning models like support vector machines (SVMs) classify interference types for mitigation [27], while unsupervised methods such as clustering detect anomalies in radar signals.

Deep learning models, are particularly effective for reconstructing the radar signals (both in time and frequency domain) [18], [21], [25], [29], [38], [43], [48], [53], [54], [58]–[61]. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs), are particularly effective for complex interference scenarios. For example, CNNs have been used to identify and classify interference patterns in automotive radar [57]. These models are trained on large datasets and can learn complex patterns and features in the data, making them well-suited for interference mitigation in challenging environments. For example, a CNN-based system trained on diverse automotive radar datasets can achieve high accuracy in interference suppression but requires significant computational resources.

III. DATASET

The availability and quality of datasets are crucial for the development and evaluation of radar interference mitigation techniques. Datasets provide the necessary data for training, testing, and benchmarking various algorithms and methods. In the context of radar interference mitigation, datasets should capture a wide range of interference scenarios, including mutual interference between automotive radars, clutter from wind turbines, and multi-path propagation in urban areas.

A. Types of Datasets

- **Synthetic Datasets:** These are generated using simulation tools and models to create controlled interference scenarios. Synthetic datasets are valuable for initial testing and development of algorithms, as they allow for precise control over the parameters and conditions. For example, synthetic datasets can simulate various types of interference, such as FMCW radar interference, to evaluate the performance of different mitigation techniques.
- **Real-World Datasets:** These are collected from actual radar systems operating in real environments. Real-world datasets provide a more accurate representation of the challenges faced by radar systems, including unpredictable interference patterns and environmental factors. For instance, datasets collected from automotive radars in urban traffic conditions can capture the complexity of mutual interference in dense vehicular networks.
- **Hybrid Datasets:** These combine synthetic and real-world data to leverage the advantages of both. Hybrid datasets can provide a comprehensive evaluation

framework by incorporating controlled scenarios from synthetic data and realistic conditions from real-world data. This approach helps in developing robust algorithms that perform well in diverse environments.

B. Key Datasets in Radar Interference Mitigation

- **Automotive Radar Datasets:** These datasets capture interference scenarios in automotive applications, such as mutual interference between radars in multi-lane traffic and cross-interference from nearby vehicles. Examples include the COSMOS Radar RobotCar Dataset [7], the ARIM Dataset [63], Raw ADC data [8], [62], which provide extensive data for developing and testing interference mitigation techniques in autonomous driving.
- **Weather Radar Datasets:** These datasets focus on interference scenarios in weather radar systems, such as clutter from wind turbines and multi-path propagation. The NEXRAD Dataset [9] is a valuable resource for researchers working on weather radar interference mitigation, offering a large collection of radar data from the National Weather Service.
- **Maritime Radar Datasets:** These datasets capture interference scenarios in maritime environments, such as reflections from waves and interference from other vessels. The C-CORE Radar Dataset [10] provides data for developing and testing interference mitigation techniques in maritime navigation and surveillance.

C. Challenges in Dataset Collection

- **Data Diversity:** Ensuring that datasets capture a wide range of interference scenarios is essential for developing robust algorithms. This includes variations in radar types, operating conditions, and environmental factors. For example, automotive radar datasets should include data from different traffic conditions, weather conditions, and vehicle types to provide a comprehensive evaluation framework.
- **Data Quality:** High-quality data is crucial for accurate training and evaluation of algorithms. This includes ensuring that the data is free from noise and artifacts that could impact the performance of interference mitigation techniques. For instance, weather radar datasets should be carefully processed to remove any spurious signals or artifacts that could affect
- **Data Quality:** High-quality data is crucial for accurate training and evaluation of algorithms. This includes ensuring that the data is free from noise and artifacts that could impact the performance of interference mitigation techniques. For instance, weather radar datasets should be carefully processed to remove any spurious signals or artifacts that could affect the accuracy of the data.
- **Data Annotation:** Annotating datasets with accurate labels and metadata is essential for supervised learning algorithms. This includes labeling different types of interference, such as mutual interference, clutter, and multi-path propagation. For example, automotive radar datasets should include annotations for different types of

interference, such as interference from nearby vehicles, reflections from road surfaces, and clutter from roadside objects.

D. Future Directions in Dataset Development

- **Standardization:** Developing standardized datasets for benchmarking and evaluation is crucial for advancing the field of radar interference mitigation. Standardized datasets provide a common framework for comparing the performance of different algorithms and techniques. This includes defining standard metrics for evaluating interference suppression efficiency, computational complexity, and implementation feasibility.
- **Open Access:** Making datasets publicly available to the research community can accelerate the development of new interference mitigation techniques. Open access datasets provide researchers with the necessary data to develop and test their algorithms, fostering collaboration and innovation. For example, initiatives like the IEEE Dataport provide a platform for sharing and accessing radar datasets.
- **Collaborative Efforts:** Collaboration between academia, industry, and government agencies can enhance the quality and diversity of radar datasets. Collaborative efforts can leverage the expertise and resources of different stakeholders to collect and curate comprehensive datasets. For instance, partnerships between automotive manufacturers, research institutions, and regulatory agencies can lead to the development of high-quality automotive radar datasets.

By addressing these challenges and focusing on future directions, the radar community can develop high-quality datasets that support the advancement of interference mitigation techniques. These datasets will play a crucial role in ensuring the reliable operation of radar systems in increasingly complex environments.

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Performance Analysis

Classical methods, such as bandpass filtering, are simple and computationally efficient, making them ideal for systems with constrained processing power. However, they are often inadequate for complex interference scenarios like multi-path propagation in urban areas. Advanced methods, particularly those using ML, demonstrate superior performance. For instance, a deep learning-based system trained on diverse automotive radar datasets can achieve high accuracy in interference suppression but requires significant computational resources. Filtering techniques, such as bandpass filters, are widely used in radar systems to isolate desired signals and suppress interference. These filters are designed to pass signals within a specific frequency range while attenuating signals outside this range. For example, in FMCW radars, bandpass filters can target specific frequency ranges to isolate desired signals and reduce interference from other sources. Spatial filtering, on the other hand, uses beamforming techniques to nullify interference from known directions. Phased array radar

systems, for instance, use spatial filters to track aircraft while ignoring ground clutter. While effective in many scenarios, these techniques may struggle with dynamic and complex interference patterns [49]. Time-domain gating is another classical approach that mitigates interference by identifying and removing corrupted time segments. Pulsed radars, for example, can discard segments of the signal that overlap with interference. While this approach is simple and effective, it is less suitable for scenarios with continuous interference, such as urban vehicular environments. In such cases, more advanced techniques are required to achieve effective interference mitigation. Interpolation algorithms, such as linear interpolation, spline interpolation, and polynomial interpolation, can be used to reconstruct missing or corrupted segments of the time-domain signal, providing a continuous and smooth signal. These algorithms are particularly useful in scenarios where the interference is intermittent and can be isolated in the time domain [2]. Compressed sensing is a powerful technique for radar signal reconstruction, exploiting the sparsity of the signal in some domain. Compressed sensing algorithms, such as convex optimization, greedy algorithms, and Bayesian methods, can reconstruct the signal with high accuracy from a limited number of samples. For example, convex optimization algorithms, such as Basis Pursuit, solve an optimization problem to find the sparsest solution that fits the observed data. Greedy algorithms, such as Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP), iteratively select the most significant components of the signal to reconstruct it. Bayesian methods, such as Bayesian Compressive Sensing (BCS), use probabilistic models to estimate the signal and its sparsity pattern. These algorithms have been successfully applied to radar signal reconstruction, providing accurate and efficient interference mitigation [12]. Adaptive signal processing techniques, such as Wiener filtering and least mean squares (LMS) algorithms, dynamically adjust to changing interference patterns, enhancing robustness. For example, Wiener filtering can optimize the signal-to-noise ratio in dynamic scenarios like naval radar systems facing multipath interference. These adaptive techniques are particularly useful in environments where interference characteristics change rapidly, requiring real-time adjustments to maintain radar performance [3]. Machine learning (ML) techniques are increasingly employed for interference mitigation. Supervised learning models, such as support vector machines (SVMs), classify interference types for mitigation, while unsupervised methods, such as clustering, detect anomalies in radar signals. Deep learning models, including convolutional neural networks (CNNs), are particularly effective for complex interference scenarios. For example, CNNs have been used to identify interference patterns in automotive radar and predict optimal suppression strategies. The ability of ML models to learn from large datasets and adapt to new interference patterns makes them a powerful tool for radar interference mitigation. However, these models require significant computational resources and large amounts of labeled data for training [55]. Interference mitigation with communication techniques, such as RadarMAC, RadCom and RadChat, leverages the communication capabilities

of radar systems to coordinate and mitigate interference. RadCom integrates radar and communication functionalities to reduce mutual interference, using frequency division multiplexing to separate radar and communication signals. RadChat is a distributed networking protocol designed to mitigate interference among FMCW-based automotive radars, using radar and communication cooperation to coordinate radar transmissions and reduce mutual interference. These techniques can significantly improve the performance and reliability of radar systems in dense environments [14], [15]. Hardware approaches, such as special design in transceivers and other hardware-related solutions, also play a crucial role in interference mitigation. For example, transceivers with high linearity and low phase noise can reduce the impact of interference on radar performance. Additionally, advanced antenna designs, such as phased array antennas [17], [19], can provide better spatial filtering and beamforming capabilities, enhancing the radar's ability to isolate desired signals and suppress interference. These hardware approaches complement the signal-processing-based techniques, providing a comprehensive solution for radar interference mitigation [26], [28], [31], [32], [36], [37], [49], [52]. In summary, while classical methods provide a foundation for interference mitigation, advanced techniques leveraging machine learning, compressed sensing, communication capabilities, and hardware innovations offer significant promise. Each approach has its strengths and limitations, and the choice of technique depends on the specific application and interference scenario. Future research should focus on developing hybrid approaches that combine the strengths of multiple techniques, addressing scalability and real-time implementation challenges, and leveraging advancements in hardware and communication technologies to enhance radar performance in increasingly complex environments.

B. Challenges

- 1) **Real-Time Implementation:** Advanced techniques often struggle with real-time constraints. For instance, deploying a deep learning model on an automotive radar may exceed processing time requirements in high-speed scenarios. Real-time implementation is critical for applications such as collision avoidance in autonomous vehicles, where timely and accurate detection of obstacles is essential for safety.
- 2) **Scalability:** Integrating ML-based methods into large-scale systems, such as nationwide air traffic management, demands extensive data and model generalization to diverse conditions. Scalability is a significant challenge, as it requires the development of models that can handle a wide range of interference scenarios and adapt to different environments.
- 3) **Hardware Limitations:** Deploying complex algorithms in resource-constrained environments, such as compact drones, requires optimizing for power and memory efficiency. Hardware limitations can impact the feasibility of implementing advanced interference mitigation techniques, particularly in applications where size, weight, and power constraints are critical.

C. Research Gaps

- 1) Improved algorithms for real-time operation, such as lightweight neural networks. Developing efficient algorithms that can operate in real-time is essential for applications where timely response is critical. Lightweight neural networks, for example, can provide a balance between performance and computational efficiency, making them suitable for real-time interference mitigation.
- 2) Hybrid approaches combining classical and advanced techniques, for instance, using adaptive filtering alongside machine learning-based anomaly detection. Hybrid approaches can leverage the strengths of both classical and advanced methods, providing robust and efficient interference mitigation. For example, adaptive filtering can be used to dynamically adjust to changing interference patterns, while machine learning-based anomaly detection can identify and mitigate complex interference scenarios.
- 3) Standardized datasets for benchmarking, such as publicly available radar datasets capturing diverse interference scenarios. The availability of standardized datasets is crucial for benchmarking and evaluating the performance of different interference mitigation techniques. These datasets should capture a wide range of interference scenarios, including mutual interference between automotive radars, clutter from wind turbines, and multi-path propagation in urban areas.
- 4) Improved data collection methods to enhance the quality and diversity of radar datasets. This includes developing advanced sensor technologies and data acquisition systems that can capture high-resolution radar data in various environments. For example, automotive radar datasets should include data from different traffic conditions, weather conditions, and vehicle types to provide a comprehensive evaluation framework.
- 5) Enhanced data annotation techniques to ensure accurate labeling of interference types. This includes developing automated annotation tools that can accurately label different types of interference, such as mutual interference, clutter, and multi-path propagation. For example, automotive radar datasets should include annotations for different types of interference, such as interference from nearby vehicles, reflections from road surfaces, and clutter from roadside objects.

By addressing these research gaps, the radar community can develop more effective and efficient interference mitigation techniques, ensuring the reliable operation of radar systems in increasingly complex environments.

V. CONCLUSION

Radar interference mitigation is vital for the reliable operation of modern radar systems. While classical techniques provide a foundation, advanced methods leveraging machine learning offer significant promise. For instance, combining spatial filtering with CNN-based interference classification can improve performance in dense urban environments. Future

research should focus on addressing scalability and real-time implementation challenges, such as developing efficient hardware accelerators for ML models. By bridging existing gaps, the radar community can ensure robust performance in increasingly complex environments.

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